

**INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION, DEMOGRAPHIC
VARIABLES AND RELATIONAL MAINTENANCE
AMONG UNMARRIED POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS OF
OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE-IFE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract:

The study ascertained the level of relational maintenance among unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife and as well as the relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife. Finally, it also examined the relationship between demographic variables and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students. These were with a view to providing useful information on relational maintenance among the unmarried postgraduate students. The study adopted survey design. The sample size comprised 600 postgraduate students selected from six selected faculties out of the thirteen Faculties in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, using multistage sampling technique. Thereafter, a total of 100 students were selected in each faculty using purposive sampling technique for those that were into dating relationship. One adapted and one self-constructed instruments were used to elicit information from the respondents. The adapted instrument was Relational Maintenance Scale (RMS) while Interpersonal Communication Inventory (ICI) was self-constructed. Percentages, frequency counts Pearson correlation and Chi-square were employed to analyze the data. The results showed that 24.8%, 52.5% and 22.7% of postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo Universities Ile-Ife demonstrated low, moderate and high levels of relational maintenance respectively. The study also indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance ($r = 0.676$, $p > 0.05$). Furthermore, the results showed significant relationship between sex of

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the students and relational maintenance ($\chi^2 = 24.271$; $df = 564$, $p > 0.05$). Finally, the results showed significant relationship between age of the students and relational maintenance ($\chi^2 = 47.837^a$; $df = 564$, $p > 0.05$). It was concluded that irrespective of the age of the students, most unmarried postgraduate students in the study area had moderate level of relational maintenance.

Keywords: relational maintenance, interpersonal communication, demographic variables and postgraduate student

1. Introduction

Relational maintenance among unmarried postgraduate students is what brings joy and satisfaction to them as they keep their relationship in a satisfactory condition. It is not enough to be connected with their intending marriage partners; they must also endeavour to maintain that connection. Dinda (2000) opined that relational maintenance is a relationship that not only continues but is also stable. Maintaining relationship is healthy and satisfying for unmarried postgraduate students, as no one enjoys unstable relationship. For many unmarried partners, relational longevity or maintenance equals success, and reflects years of interaction patterns that have somehow led to stability. More precisely, many unmarried partners are continuously using a variety of behaviours to effectively maintain their relationships. Stafford and Canary (1991) defined relational maintenance as "*efforts expended to maintain the nature of the relationship to the actor's satisfaction.*" Dinda (2003) offered a similar definition referring to relational maintenance behaviours as "conscious and intentional behaviours designed to maintain the relationship. Guerrero (2000), in his study of intimacy, expressed that unmarried partners who engage in relational maintenance behaviours may experience increased individual well-being when those behaviours appear to be successful but decreased well-being when they appear to be unsuccessful.

Rath and Harter (2010) and Robles, Slatcher, Tombello, & McGinn (2014) affirmed the positive impacts on the health, life satisfaction, and happiness of individuals that have a maintained relationship. Similarly, Guerrero, Elov and Wabnik (1993) findings revealed that partners who reported high or moderate levels of relational maintenance were more satisfied with their relationships. Relationship maintenance has also been described as a dynamic process that assists in preserving a relationship (Dindia, 2000). This is because relationship that is not preserved will deteriorate. The relational maintenance process involves performing symbolic behaviours that communicate a person's desire to continue a relationship, often referred to as maintenance strategies (Bryant & Marmo, 2009). Relationship maintenance entails actions or behaviours that individuals engage in to sustain a specified relational state (Canary & Dainton, 2006). For example, two long distant friends may engage in weekly phone calls to keep their friendship alive or spouses may visit a therapist to revitalize

their commitment. These strategies will keep the relationship going and stable because without it, relationships will naturally disintegrate and deteriorate.

Most times, it appears that most dating relationships among postgraduate students end in deadlock because of the inability of the partners to fulfil their responsibilities. This may result to emotional breakdown, poor academic performances, loneliness and suicide attempt. Several cases have been reported of students' committing suicide after a breakup in their relationship. An investigation was reported on March 6, 2014 by Vanguard News Paper of a university male student who committed suicide after being jilted by his female partner. In the opinion of Dinda (2002), individuals are likely to maintain their relationship with their partners depending on strategies and behaviours designed to keep the relationship going. It is therefore opined that relational maintenance of an individual is a function of several variables such as interpersonal communication and demographics.

Interpersonal communication may be seen as an essential ingredient of a stable relationship, as this serves as a process in which individuals convey information, exchange ideas and have knowledge of each other. Studies have shown that the level of stability in a relationship depends on the degree of interpersonal communication between individuals that are interdependent (Miller & Tedder 2011, Mackey, Diemer, & O'Brien, 2004, Christine 2008). Knapp and Augustine (2002) stated that interpersonal communication can mean the ability to relate to people in written as well as verbal communication. This type of communication can occur in both a one-on-one and a group setting. This also means being able to handle different people in different situations, and making people feel at ease. Gestures such as eye contact, body movement, and hand gestures are also part of interpersonal communication. The most common functions of interpersonal communication are listening, talking and conflict resolution (Deutsch, 2000). Interpersonal communication between unmarried partners is an essential ingredient for maintaining relationship. When thoughts and feelings flow smoothly between partners, there is fun and they both feel good. Moreover, when communication is blocked, pressure builds up. Overtime, lack of communication flow dries up the trust and love between the partners. A research conducted by Adler, Rosenfeld and Proctor, (2001) also stated that partners must therefore clearly understand the power of communication in maintaining their relationship and must be aware of each other and consider each other.

Interpersonal communication is the starting point of all relationships between living things. Only human communication enjoys a rich diversity of sounds, symbols, actions, attitudes and thoughts which has enabled humanity to obtain mastery of the known world and to open the gateways of the universe to explanation (Searle, 2000). Indeed, the basis or foundation of all human relations is communication. Everything that people acquire arises from their ability to communicate with one another. It is the cement that stabilizes and upholds a human being's existence within a family, social group, community, nation and the world at large. Communication is not only a person's way of expressing his or her humanity, dignity, needs, strengths, objectives

and concern for other people; it comprises the very bricks and mortar that build civilizations (Searle, 2004). Guerrero, Anderson and Afifi, (2011) found that interpersonal communication is one of the most basic elements in human functioning because it is the cornerstone of stable and healthy interpersonal relationship through which relationships are formed and maintained. In the same vein, Turnbull (2010) claimed that interpersonal communication is one of the basic needs of any interpersonal relationship as it prevents the relationship from being broken.

In a stable relationship, partners talk freely, openly, and feel safe sharing their most private thoughts with each other. They comfortably and considerately verbalize their concerns and feelings when difficulties arise and voice their positive thoughts when things are good. Both partners talk tactfully, staying far from attacking, hurtful or controlling comments. They listen attentively, trying to understand what their partner says with sympathy rather than looking for what is wrong in what their partner has to say or dismissing what they hear, even if they have a different perspective. Moreover, after talking, both people in the courtship feel good about the conversation, and feel like their concerns have been considered and addressed. Conflict has been seen as a common characteristic in personal relationships. Wilmot and Hocker (2011) defined conflict as *“an expressed struggle between at least two interdependent parties who perceive incompatible goals, scarce resources, and interference from the other party in achieving their goals.”* Intending marriage partners in a relationship can have conflicts about many issues, although it is not fun, but it may be healthy for a lasting relationship. The way couples handle conflict—rather than the number of conflicts they experience—is what influences the success of their relationship.

Another major issue in literature relates to how demographic factors such as age and sex can determine relational maintenance. It is an interesting phenomenon that attempts to explain how students of different sexes maintain their relationships. For years, the significance of an individual sex in relation to maintaining relationship with partners have been subjected to enthusiastic debates, discussions and research in psychology as well as other discipline, but the difficulty of this issue is that it is scientifically difficult to determine and support. Some researchers have reported that females reported higher levels of maintenance behaviours than males. For instance, Igarashi, Takai, and Yoshida, (2005) found that females employ more maintenance strategies than males. In the same vein, Dindia (2000) adds that females are *“relationship specialists,”* in that both males and females perceive females to be more relationally oriented. Another study conducted by Ogolsky, (2007) also affirmed that females employ higher levels of maintenance behaviours than males. Reid and Reid (2008) and Faulkner and Culwin (2005) also concurred with the above findings that females exhibit more relational maintenance behaviour than males. Moreover, Aylor and Dainton (2004) reported that females utilize more relational maintenance strategies than males. Canary and Stafford (1992) reported females use openness, social networks, and shared tasks more than male. This is because females generally tend to self-disclose, more sociable, sensitive, and motivated to create and maintain relationships,

develop emotional bonds and use more relationship-oriented language and symbols within relationships than males. Contrary to the above findings, the finding of Baber (2012) contradicts what previous studies have found about males and females in maintaining relationship. It was discovered that males are in fact using text messages to communicate the relational maintenance strategy of openness more often than females. This is different than what previous studies have found.

Also, some researchers have reported that the age of dating partners impacted on their relational maintenance while the opinion of others differed on the issue. For instance Bradbury, Fincham, & Beach, (2000) found a strong correlation between the two variables. That is, there is significant positive relationship between age of the dating partners and relational maintenance. In the same vein, Umberson, Williams, Powers, Chen, Campbell (2005), found a positive association between ages as evidenced in longevity of relationship. Contrary to the above, the result of the study on age, education level, and length of courtship in relation to marital satisfaction conducted by Emily in (2010) indicated that there was no significant relationship between age and relational maintenance. Consequent upon this, the study is designed to ascertain the extent of relationship between interpersonal communication demographic variables and relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students.

2. Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives were to:

- 1) ascertain the level of relational maintenance among unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University;
- 2) investigate the relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students and
- 3) examine the relationship between each of sex and age and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students.

3. Methodology

The study employed the descriptive survey design. The population for the study consisted of postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. The sample size comprised of 600 postgraduate students who were selected from six faculties out of the thirteen faculties in the school. The multistage and purposive techniques were employed to select the study sample. Thereafter, 100 postgraduate students were selected in each faculty using purposive sampling technique for those that were into dating relationship. The instruments were administered on the respondents in their various lecture classes. Two research instruments used to collect data were: Relational Maintenance Scale (RMS) and Interpersonal Communication Inventory (ICI). RMS was 20-item instrument adapted from the work of Funk and Rogge (2006), while ICI contained 20 items that was self-constructed. The Spearman

Brown Coefficients and Spearman Brown Split-half reliability tests conducted on the instruments showed that RMS yielded results of 0.85 and 0.91 while, ICI had 0.90 and 0.95. Both at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive statistics and Pearson product correlation method and chi-square were employed to analyse the data

4. Results

4.1 Research Question One

What is the level of relational maintenance among unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife?

Table 1: Levels of Relational Maintenance among the postgraduate students

Levels	Frequency (N=564)	Percentage (%)
Low	140	24.8
Moderate	296	52.5
High	128	22.7
Total	564	100.0

Table 1 shows the distribution of the level of relational maintenance among postgraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. It can be further inferred, that 24.8% of postgraduate students had low level of relational maintenance, and 52.5% of the students had moderate level of relational maintenance while the remaining 22.7% had high level of relational maintenance. The finding of this study indicated that more than half of the postgraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University had moderate level of relational maintenance.

Research Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

Table 2: Correlation between Interpersonal Communication and Relational Maintenance among the Postgraduate students

	$\bar{x}$	SD	N	r-cal p
Interpersonal Communication	67.2004	8.12395	564	0.676** .000
Relational Maintenance	70.0709	8.59369	564	P < 0.05

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 2 shows the result of relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students. As shown in Table, the correlation coefficient (r) between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance is 0.676. This value is found to be significant at 0.05 probability level. This suggests that there is a positive and significant relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance.

Research Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between age and relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-Square Analysis of Relationship between Age and Relational Maintenance among the Postgraduate students

	Age Range			Total	χ^2	df	P
	20-25	26-30	31 and above				
Low	4	92	36	132	47.837 ^a	4	.000
Moderate	84	184	40	308			
High	20	68	36	124			
Total	108	344	112	564			

Table 2 shows the result of relationship between age and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students. From the table it can be observed that a Chi-square test indicated a significant relationship between age and relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students, $\chi^2 (n = 564) = 47.837$, $df = 4$, $p = .000$. This value is found to be significant at 0.05 probability level. This suggests that there is a significant relationship between age and relational maintenance.

There is no significant relationship between sex and relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-Square Analysis of Relationship between Sex and Relational Maintenance among Postgraduate Students

		Total_Rational_Maintenance			N	df	χ^2	P
		Low	Moderate	High				
Sex	Male	100	156	68	324	24.271	.000	
	Female	32	152	56	240			
Total		132	308	124	564			

$p < 0.05$ (significant)

Table 4 shows relationship results between sex and relational maintenance among unmarried postgraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. It was revealed that, the χ^2_{cal} of 0.166; $df = 564$, $p < 0.05$ was significant. This rejected the null hypothesis which stated that there was significant relationship between sex and relational maintenance among the postgraduate students.

5. Discussion of Findings

The present study examined the relationship between interpersonal communication, demographic variables and relational maintenance among unmarried postgraduate

students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. Most postgraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife have been found to possess moderate level of relational maintenance. The findings supported the work of previous researchers, Guerrero, Elov and Wabnik (1993) finding that partners who reported high or moderate levels of relational maintenance are more satisfied with their relationship. Consistent with these results, Guerrero (2000) and (Floyd, Hesse, & Haynes, 2007) also affirmed that it is tremendously beneficial for individuals to maintain a stable relationship with their dating partners. Similarly, Robles, Slatcher, Tombello, & McGinn, (2014) affirmed the positive impacts on the health, life satisfaction, and happiness of individuals that has a maintained relationship. Therefore, it seems logical to agree with the findings of Rath and Harter (2010) that relational maintenance is vital to health, happiness, well-being and even productivity of dating partners. This implies that unmarried postgraduate students with moderate level of relational maintenance stand a better chance of maintaining their relationship.

It was also discovered in this study that there is significant relationship between interpersonal communication and relational maintenance among the unmarried postgraduate students, which may enhance the quality of their relationship and prevent their relationships from getting deteriorated. This buttress the point raised by Miller and Tedder (2011) that partners who experienced positive communication and have knowledge of each other are more satisfied in their relationship than partners who did not. Research by Mackey, Diemer, and O'Brien, (2004) also showed that interpersonal communication is associated with relationship quality. Consequent upon this, it is good to note that interpersonal communication is sine-qua-non to relational maintenance between unmarried partners. Confirming this statement, Hybels & Weaver (2009) maintained that interpersonal communication brings greater satisfaction to individuals in a close personal relationship. This result is in consonance with the findings of Bryant and Marmo (2009) which indicated that the process of relational maintenance involves performing symbolic behaviours that communicate a person's desire to continue the relationship. In line with this, Dinda (2003) also stated that keeping relationship in a satisfactory condition requires conscious and intentional behaviours designed to maintain the nature of relationship to the actor's satisfaction. Guerrero, Anderson and Afifi, (2011) revealed in their study that communication is the substance of relationships, without it there is no relationship. Therefore, the quality of communication is important in determining the outcome of the relationship. When there is poor communication and conflicts arise, the way in which a couple handles the conflict is key.

According to Gottman (1999), a well-renowned relationship expert revealed in his work that satisfied couples are more likely to discuss issues of disagreement, whereas dissatisfied couples are likely to minimize or avoid conflict. (Guerrero, et al., 2011) also opined that the way partners manage conflict is a better predictor of relationship satisfaction, than the experience of the conflict itself. In other words, better communication is related to better relational maintenance, whereas poor

communication is associated with poor relationship instability. The results indicated that communication is one of the important indicators not only of relationship satisfaction, but also of relationship stability. Research conducted by Christine (2008) affirmed that the quality of communication between two individuals is an essential determinant of relationship longevity. To buttress this point, Adler, Rosenfeld and Proctor, (2001) also stated that partners must therefore clearly understand the power of communication in maintaining their relationship and must be aware of each other and consider each other. Guerrero, Anderson and Afifi, (2011) found that interpersonal communication is one of the most basic elements in human functioning because it is the cornerstone of stable and healthy interpersonal relationship through which relationships are formed and maintained. In the same vein, Turnbull (2010) claimed that interpersonal communication is one of the basic needs of any interpersonal relationship as it prevents the relationship from being broken.

Further, the findings revealed that there is significant relationship between sex and relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students. The result is in line with the findings of Igarashi, Takai, and Yoshida, (2005) who affirmed that females employ more maintenance strategies than males. In the same vein, Dindia (2000) adds that females are “relationship specialists,” in that both males and females perceive females to be more relationally oriented.

For this reason, women are more responsible for relationship maintenance, do it more often, and are better at it. Another study conducted by Ogolsky, (2007) also found that females employ higher levels of maintenance behaviors than did males. Reid and Reid (2008) and Faulkner and Culwin (2005) also concur with the above findings that females exhibit more relational maintenance behaviour than males. This is because females generally tend to be more sociable, sensitive, self-disclose and motivated to create and maintain relationships, develop emotional bonds and use more relationship-oriented language and symbols within relationships than males. Contrary to the above findings, the finding of Baber (2012) contradicts what previous studies have found about males and females in maintaining relationship. It was discovered that males are in fact using text messages to communicate the relational maintenance strategy of openness more often than females. This is different from the result of this study.

In conclusion, the results of the hypothesis two showed there was positive relationship between age and relational maintenance of unmarried partners. The result of this study is supported by Bradbury, Fincham, and Beach, (2000) findings that there is a statistical significant relationship between age and relational maintenance or longevity. That is, the age of the partner is sine-qua-non in maintaining relationship. Also supporting the statement, Umberson, Williams, Powers, Chen, Campbell (2005) and Levenson, Carstenson, & Gottman, 1993 also found positive associations between ages as evidenced in longevity of relationship. In his findings, Emily's (2010) remarked that, there was no statistical significant relationship between age and relational maintenance among dating and married partners. Considering the fact that there was no consensus of opinion among the scholars, the inference that can be made is that, this

may be unique to these respondents, or there may be an extraneous variable that was not identified by the questionnaire. Also, it is possible that with a larger sample size there would have been more of a variety of ages represented. Perhaps a sample more representative of the population would have yielded different results.

6. Conclusion/recommendations

Arising from the above findings, it can thus be concluded that most unmarried postgraduate students in the study area had moderate level of relational maintenance and this had predisposed them to be emotionally and psychologically stable. Besides, it can also be concluded that interpersonal communication between unmarried partners plays a vital role in maintaining relationship among unmarried postgraduate students. Also, findings indicated that the two demographic variables considered were significantly related to relational maintenance of unmarried postgraduate students. In view of the above, it is recommended that unmarried postgraduate students to develop interpersonal communication with their partners as barrier against breakup.

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